

THE EFFECT OF THE GASTRONOMY AND COOKERY STUDENTS' NEOPHOBIC AND NEOPHILIC TENDENCIES ON THEIR ATTITUDES TOWARD THE STREET FLAVORS

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Abstract

The trends for food neophobia and food neophilia can affect people's attitudes toward new foods. In this context, different regional street foods they have never consumed before can also be an unusual food experience for people. Street foods, which are foods and beverages offered in public areas, reflecting the culinary culture of countries with a rich and different product range, may differ from region to region and even according to the distinct geographical location and seasonal characteristics of the same territory. This study reveals the effects of food neophobia and food neophilia tendencies of gastronomy and cookery students on their attitudes toward street foods. The study concluded that food neophobia and food neophilia trends were linearly and positively related to the attitudes toward street foods. However, significant differences were found in students' neophobia and neophilia tendencies and their attitudes toward street foods according to demographic characteristics. In addition, it was determined that the students continued to consume street foods even though they did not find them hygienic. On the other hand, the study revealed that the students had a neophilia tendency.

Keywords: Neophobia; Neophilia; Street foods; Gastronomy Students; Cookery Students; Phrygia.

O EFEITO DAS TENDÊNCIAS NEOFÓBICAS E NEOFÍLICAS DOS ESTUDANTES DE GASTRONOMIA E CULINÁRIA SOBRE SUAS ATITUDES EM RELAÇÃO AOS SABORES DE RUA

Resumo

As tendências de neofobia alimentar e neofilia alimentar podem afetar as atitudes das pessoas em relação a novos alimentos. Neste contexto, diferentes alimentos de rua regionais que nunca consumiram antes também podem ser uma experiência alimentar incomum para as pessoas. Os alimentos de rua, que são alimentos e bebidas oferecidos em áreas públicas, refletindo a cultura culinária de países com uma gama rica e diferente de produtos, podem diferir de região para região e até mesmo de acordo com a localização geográfica distinta e características sazonais do mesmo território. Este estudo revela os efeitos da neofobia alimentar e das tendências alimentares de estudantes de gastronomia e culinária sobre suas atitudes em relação aos alimentos de rua. O estudo concluiu que as tendências de neofobia alimentar e neofilia alimentar estavam linearmente e positivamente relacionadas às atitudes em relação aos alimentos de rua. No entanto, diferenças significativas foram encontradas nas tendências de neofobia e neofilia dos alunos e suas atitudes em relação aos alimentos de rua de acordo com características demográficas. Além disso, foi determinado que os alunos continuaram a consumir alimentos de rua, mesmo não os encontrando higiênicos. Por outro lado, o estudo revelou que os alunos tinham uma tendência de neofilia.

Palavras chave: Neofobia; Neofilia; Comida de rua; Estudantes de gastronomia; Estudantes de culinária; Frígia.

EL EFECTO DE LAS TENDENCIAS NEOFÓBICAS Y NEOFÍLICAS DE LOS ESTUDIANTES DE GASTRONOMÍA Y COCINA EN SUS ACTITUDES HACIA LOS SABORES DE LA CALLE

Resumen

Las tendencias de la neofobia alimentaria y la neofilia alimentaria pueden afectar las actitudes de las personas hacia los nuevos alimentos. En este contexto, diferentes comidas callejeras regionales que nunca han consumido antes también pueden ser una experiencia gastronómica inusual para las personas. Los alimentos callejeros, que son alimentos y bebidas ofrecidos en áreas públicas, que reflejan la cultura culinaria de países con una gama de productos rica y diferente, pueden diferir de una región a otra e incluso según la ubicación geográfica distinta y las características estacionales del mismo territorio. Este estudio revela los efectos de la neofobia alimentaria y las tendencias de neofilia alimentaria de los estudiantes de gastronomía y cocina en sus actitudes hacia los alimentos callejeros. El estudio concluyó que las tendencias de la neofobia alimentaria y la neofilia alimentaria estaban lineal y positivamente relacionadas con las actitudes hacia los alimentos callejeros. Sin embargo, se encontraron diferencias significativas en las tendencias de neofobia y neofilia de los estudiantes y sus actitudes hacia los alimentos callejeros de acuerdo con las características demográficas. Además, se determinó que los estudiantes continuaron consumiendo alimentos callejeros a pesar de que no los encontraban higiénicos. Por otro lado, el estudio reveló que los estudiantes tenían una tendencia a la neofilia.

Palabras clave: Neofobia, Neofilia; Comida callejera; Estudiantes de Gastronomía; Estudiantes de Cocina; Frígia.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nutrition is one of the most basic needs of humans. Food and beverages shape people's eating habits (Yiğit & Dogdubay, 2017). People may display natural attitudes such as dissatisfaction with new and unknown/exotic foods, suspicion about them, or on the contrary, may tend to seek novelty and variety. In other words, people may be afraid of innovation in their food preferences or may pursue original and foreign foods. These two tendencies appear as

behavioral personality traits as "Food Neophobia" and "Food Neophilia."

Fear of novelty in food (Neophobia) manifests itself as doubting unfamiliar cuisines, avoiding meals with unknown ingredients, and identifying different cultural foods and beverages as weird. Novelty seeking in food (Neophilia), however, refers to a willingness to experience original/exotic foods, try authentic recipes and cuisine cultures, and consume exotic foods (Rızaoğlu et al., 2013).

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When individuals become familiar with foreign foods in time, their attitudes towards foreign tastes may differ. Besides, although eating known foods provides convenience and confidence in daily nutrition, it leads to mediocrity in eating habits over time. This tendency reduces the willingness to consume new/unfamiliar foods (Dovey et al. 2008: 185).

Food neophobia affects not only people's daily diet but also their professional careers if they work in the food and beverage sector. A neophobic personality of an individual working in the kitchen may cause some difficulties. In particular, a higher neophobia tendency than neophilia in gastronomy and cookery students, who are future chefs, may cause a professional disadvantage.

Food neophobia is a significant obstacle for future chefs in preparing new menus with new products, developing creativity, experiencing different country cuisines, developing their palate, and developing unusual gastronomic trends such as fusion cuisine.

On the other hand, street delicacies are one of the food and beverage groups that individuals display different approaches. Worldwide, about 2.5 billion people consume street foods every day (FAO, 2012). Street delicacies are the integral culinary culture parts of countries as well as being traditional representatives of fast food movements; they create a nutritional culture with a wide variety of traditional, regional, and seasonal meals, reflecting ethnic diversity (Calloni, 2013).

In addition, people prefer street tastes because they present a splendid variety and content, high quality, easy availability, simplicity, and affordable prices in local tastes. Therefore, street flavors are a preference for food and beverages by all social segments (Tinker, 1999). A review of the relevant literature showed that the attitudes of individuals toward street tastes differ according to their demographic characteristics.

Street delicacies are foods frequently consumed by students because they are cheap and easy to find. For this reason, it is significant to know whether rich and diverse local Turkish street flavors affect the neophobic or neophilic food tendencies of individuals—especially students—and their attitudes toward street tastes.

In this direction, the current study investigated the effect of gastronomy and cookery students' food neophobia and neophilia tendencies on their attitudes toward street flavors. The first part of the study covered general information about food neophobia and neophilia tendencies and elaborated on the subject with the factors affecting neophobia and neophilia and the related literature studies.

The second part dealt with the definition, history, development, and importance of street tastes, their preparation and presentation methods, their economic, hygiene, and nutrition dimensions, and the situation in Türkiye, as well as mentioning the studies on street delicacies.

The third part detailed the purpose of the study, its importance, scope, limitations, the sample and universe, the scales used, and the data collection and analysis process, and presented the study results, discussions, and suggestions.

2 FOOD NEOPHOBIA AND NEOPHILIA AND STREET TASTES

Neophobia and neophilia tendencies, which appear as personality traits, are significant determinants in individuals' daily food choices. (Pliner and Hobden, 1992; Flight et al., 2003; Schnettler et al., 2013). People may exhibit natural attitudes such as dislike or doubt for new and unknown/unfamiliar foods. While neophobic individuals are more reluctant to original/exotic meals, neophilic individuals are more novelty-seeking and prefer more exotic flavors.

Street foods are ready-to-eat foods that are available everywhere and at every moment (Irigüler and Öztürk, 2016). Street flavors, which are an integral part of the food culture, are a mirror of the social, economic, and cultural differentiae of the countries. In this context, street delicacies in each country have their own characteristics.

Street flavors, shaped according to the regions' eating habits, palate, and agricultural products, also play a critical role in the science of gastronomy (Şeker, 2018). In this respect, neophobia and neophilia tendencies can change people's attitudes toward food. One of the core questions of the study is whether these trends affect the attitude toward street flavors, which contain original/exotic, rich regional foods and beverages. Therefore, a pair of hypotheses were set as follows:

H1: Students' neophobic tendencies affect their general attitudes toward street tastes.

H2: Students' neophilic tendencies affect their general attitudes toward street tastes.

Some factors—such as sensory properties, hygiene status, content knowledge about foods, and people's psychological and environmental conditions—affect food neophobia and neophilia (Pliner and Salvy, 2006; Wadolowska et al., 2008; Schnettler et al., 2013; Mak et al., 2017; Giordano et al., 2018).

On the other hand, a relevant literature examination and our analysis revealed that street flavors had sub-dimensions: food and service qualities, customer pleasure, hygiene, price, and satisfaction. One thinks that prominent sensory properties, such as high-quality foods and feelings of pleasure, reduce neophobia, while poor hygiene increases neophobic tendencies in food selections. Reportedly, food neophilia positively relates to satisfaction (Dimitrovski et al., 2017). In this respect, the following hypotheses were established to test whether the individuals' neophobia and neophilia tendencies affected the sub-dimensions of street tastes:

H3: Students' neophobic tendencies affect the sub-dimensions of street tastes.

H4: Students' neophilic tendencies affect the sub-dimensions of street tastes.

Socio-demographic factors—age, gender, education, marital status, income level, place of residence, hometown, religion, culture, and so forth—significantly affect the willingness to consume new foods (Pliner and Salvy, 2006; Stocia and Alexe, 2016).

For example, some researchers stated that since individuals living in rural areas are less likely to encounter unknown foods, these people's neophobia levels are higher

than those residing in urban areas (Tuorila et al., 2001; Ozgen, 2014; Flight et al. 2003).

The current study aimed to examine whether students' neophobic and neophilic tendencies differed according to their demographic characteristics. Since most of the students were in the same age group and their marital status was single, the evaluation of differences between these data was impossible. The following hypothesis tested whether neophobia and neophilia tendencies differed according to demographic characteristics:

H5: Neophobia and neophilia tendencies of students differ according to their demographic characteristics.

Some studies (Solunoğlu and Nazik, 2018, Akşit, 2019) on consumer attitudes and preferences toward street tastes revealed differences according to demographic characteristics. The current study's authors think, along with other demographic differences, the street flavors of the province where the students study may create differences in their attitudes. In this sense, the following hypothesis tested the effect of demographic characteristics on the general attitude toward street tastes.

H6: Students' general attitudes towards street flavors differ according to demographic characteristics.

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: own elaboration.

3 METHODOLOGY

The current study adopted a quantitative approach. The study population consists of students studying gastronomy and cookery at universities in the Phrygian touristic region. The touristic Phrygia region covers the cities of Ankara, Eskişehir, Afyonkarahisar, Kütahya, and Uşak (Ministry of Culture and Tourism Activity Report, 2008). The rich culinary culture in this region—including Afyonkarahisar, which has been registered as a gastronomy city by UNESCO—was the primary reason for selecting the Phrygian region as the research universe in this study.

Besides, different regional street flavors found together, and gastronomy and cookery programs in many universities of these cities were other reasons for this choice. In this context, the study data were collected from associate and undergraduate students studying gastronomy and cookery in these provinces. Since it was impossible to reach the whole universe (n=2519 students) due to the time, cost, and pandemic-based communication difficulties, this study preferred to collect sampling.

According to Saldamlı and Can (2019), the sample size should have min 333 participants in studies with a population size between 2500 to 3000. As understood by this statement,

for the universities in the Phrygian region with a research population of 2519 students, a minimum of 333 participants was necessary for the sampling group. The data collection method was the convenience sampling method, one of the non-probability sampling methods.

3.1 Data Collection Method

The questionnaire form prepared to collect the data comprised three parts. The first part of the questionnaire covered questions about determining the demographic characteristics of the participants (age, gender, education, etc.). The second part contained the 10-item Food Neophobia Scale developed by Pliner and Hobden (1992) to measure the participants' neophobic and neophilic tendencies. The attitude scale contains six sub-dimensions: food quality, service quality, pleasure, hygiene, price, and satisfaction. The statements in the scale were rated using a five-point Likert-type scale.

Different researchers have used this scale in the national literature (Kabaran, 2011; Rızaoğlu, Ayazlar, & Gencer, 2013; Yiğit & Doğdubay, 2017; Üzülmöz, 2018), as in the current study, because of its suitability to Turkish culture. The third part of the questionnaire employed a 25-item attitude scale developed by Chavarria and Phakdeekausorn (2017) and tested by Solunoğlu (2018) and Akşit (2019) in Turkish to determine the participants' attitudes toward street tastes.

In addition, two more questions were added to the questionnaire to determine students' street food consumption frequencies and their most consumed street flavors. After setting up the online questionnaire, the survey links were sent to gastronomy and cookery students between 5 May 2021 and 15 July 2021 via faculty members serving in the relevant departments. In this data collection process, the faculty members acted as intermediaries to deliver the links to the students.

The researchers also shared the questionnaire forms on culinary and gastronomy blogs and other social media applications, such as Instagram, Facebook, and WhatsApp, for the relevant participants to fill out. In the questionnaire created in the online environment, it was obligatory to answer all the questions.

Therefore, the collected data had no missing value. Nevertheless, two incorrectly filled questionnaires were thus removed from the dataset. As a result, 354 duly filled questionnaires were collected for data analysis.

3.2 Data Analysis Method

The study analyzed data using the techniques such as percentage and frequency analysis, arithmetic mean, and standard deviation in SPSS and AMOS statistical programs; measured validity and reliability with factor analysis and calculated Cronbach's Alpha value. The skewness and kurtosis test to determine the normality of the data showed a normal distribution of the data. While T-test and One-Way ANOVA were employed in the Difference tests, correlation and regression analyses determined the relationship between the variables.

4 RESULTS

Of the participants, 29.4% were male, 70.6% were female, 97.5% were single, 45.5% were gastronomy students, 54.5% were cookery students, 22.9% practiced internships, 43.2% lived in Afyonkarahisar, 32.8% in Ankara, 29.9% in Eskişehir, and 3.1% in Kütahya. The participants were almost the same age, and more than half of them (52.8%) were first-grader.

4.1 Measurement Model: Validity and Reliability of Scales

4.1.1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis on Neophobia and Neophilia Scales

In order to determine the validity of the Neophobia and Neophilia scales used in the research, a first-level Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted using the AMOS program. The maximum likelihood calculation method was preferred since the data were in a normal distribution. DFA acceptable fit indices are as follows: $\chi^2/df \leq 4-5$, NFI 0,94-0,90, NNFI 0,94-0,90, IFI 0,94-0,90, CFI 0,94-0,90, RMSEA 0,06-0,08, GFI 0,89-0,85, AGFI 0,89-0,80 (Anderson & Gerbing, 1984; Cole, 1987; Lhendup & Panda, 2020; Marsh and Hocevar, 1988; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013).

CFA showed that ten items and two sub-dimensions of the Neophobia and Neophilia scale were consistent with the scale structure. According to the first-level CFA results, fit index values ($\chi^2/df = 3.061$, NFI=0.900, NNFI(TLI)=0.901, IFI=0.928, CFI=0.927, RMSEA=0.076, GFI=0.945, AGFI=0.909) showed that the proposed two-factor model was in good agreement with the data. These results confirmed the predicted theoretical structure of the Neophobia and Neophilia scales.

Table 1 shows the factor loads obtained from the CFA analyses on the neophobia and neophilia scales. The factor loads were in an acceptable range between 0.431 and 0.786.

Table 1. Factor Loads and CR Values of The Neophobia and Neophilia Scales.

Factors	Expressions	Factor Loads	CR
Neophobia	NFB1	0.675	-a
	NFB2	0.548	7.783***
	NFB3	0.539	7.694***
	NFB4	0.673	8.727***
	NFB5	0.431	6.432***
Neophilia	NFL1	0.722	-a
	NFL2	0.786	12.861***
	NFL3	0.686	11.732***
	NFL4	0.529	8.705***
	NFL5	0.773	13.059

Note: * $p \leq 0.001$

Source: own elaboration.

4.1.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis on the Street Tastes Attitude Scale

In order to determine the validity of the Street Tastes Attitude Scale used in the research, a first-level Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted using the AMOS program. Since the data had a normal distribution, the Maximum Likelihood calculation method was used.

Table 2. Factor Loads and CR Values of Street Tastes Attitude Scale

Factors	Expressions	Factor Loads	CR
Food Quality	GK1	0.733	-a
	GK2	0.593	10.736***
	GK3	0.352	6.289***
	GK4	0.753	13.739***
	GK5	0.651	11.827***
	GK6	0.709	12.896***
	GK7	0.639	11.547***
Service Quality	HK1	0.524	-a
	HK2	0.535	7.747***
	HK3	0.521	7.603***
	HK4	0.713	9.173***
	HK5	0.746	9.400***
	HK6	0.729	9.292***
	HK7	0.752	9.445***
Pleasure	HA1	0.930	-a
	HA2	0.944	31.738***
	HA3	0.820	22.386***
Hygiene	HJ1	0.714	-a
	HJ2	0.920	16.977***
	HJ3	0.921	16.982***
	HJ4	0.922	17.011
Price	PD1	0.721	-a
	PD2	0.891	14.376***
Satisfaction	M1	0.861	-a
	M2	0.830	17.780***
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	PD2	0.891	14.376***
Satisfaction	M1	0.861	-a
	M2	0.830	17.780***

Source: own elaboration.

The factor loads obtained with the CFA analysis of the Street Tastes Attitude Scale. The factor loads were between 0.521 and 0.944 and were in the acceptable range.

The reliability of a scale is another essential feature in research and requires a Cronbach Alpha coefficient above 0.70 (Gürbüz and Şahin, 2018: 331). The reliability analysis showed the reliability coefficients as 0.70 on the neophobia scale and 0.81 on the neophilia scale. In addition, the reliability coefficients for the scale's sub-dimensions were (α)=0.83 in food quality, (α)=0.83 in service quality, (α)=0.92 in pleasure,

(α)=0.92 in hygiene, (α)=0.78 in price, (α)=0.83 in satisfaction. The reliability coefficient of the street tastes attitude scale was (α)=0.94. The reliability levels of the scales used in the research were higher than the acceptable value of 0.70.

Table 3 shows the correlation analysis results revealing the strength and direction of the relationship between the gastronomy and cookery students' neophobic and neophilic tendencies and their attitudes toward food quality, service quality, pleasure, hygiene, price, and satisfaction in street tastes.

Table 3: Correlation, Reliability, Mean and Standard Deviation Value.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	α	M	SD
NFB (1)	1									0.70	2.77	0.85
NFL (2)	-0.039	1								0.81	3.87	0.89
FQ (3)	0.125*	0.400**	1							0.83	3.72	0.75
SQ (4)	0.139**	0.401**	0.719**	1						0.83	3.92	0.74
PL (5)	0.069	0.453**	0.739**	0.715**	1					0.92	4.08	0.92
HGN (6)	0.098	0.154**	0.432**	0.313**	0.353**	1				0.92	2.61	0.88
PRC (7)	0.053	0.272**	0.554**	0.597**	0.582**	0.387**	1			0.78	3.99	0.94
STF(8)	0.103	0.241**	0.599**	0.584**	0.551**	0.544**	0.674**	1		0.83	3.51	0.94
STT GNL TOTAL (9)	0.134*	0.421**	0.892**	0.865**	0.833**	0.616**	0.736**	0.774**	1	0.94	3.65	0.66

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) N=354

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-pointed)

Source: own elaboration.

The correlation analysis showed that neophobia (r=0.134, p=.000<0.05) and neophilia (r=0.421, p=.000<0.01) were positively correlated with the attitude toward street tastes. In other words, as the students' neophobic and neophilic tendencies increased, the general attitude towards street tastes also increased.

While a weak correlation existed between neophobia and general attitude toward street tastes, there was a moderate relation between neophilia and general attitude toward street tastes. In addition, there were positive relationships between neophobia and food quality (r=0.125, p=.000<0.05) and neophobia and service quality (r=0.139, p=.000<0.01).

Neophilia had positive correlations with food quality (r=0.400, p=.000<0.01), service quality (r=0.401,

p=.000<0.01), pleasure (r=0.453, p=.000<0.01), hygiene (r=0.154, p=.000<0.01), price (r=0.272, p=.000<0.01), satisfaction (r=0.599, p=.000<0.01). While these relationship levels were weak in hygiene, satisfaction, and price sub-dimensions, they were moderate in other sub-dimensions. These results were similar to the results of the studies conducted by Ha Heonsu (2016), Lee et al. (2019), and Tracy et al. (2020).

The following study section covered the regression analysis results performed to support the correlation analysis results and test the study hypotheses. Since there was more than one independent variable, multiple regression analysis was employed in the study. The findings shed light on the matter of to what extent the hypotheses were supported.

Table 4. Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Neophobic and Neophilic Tendencies on General Attitudes toward Street Flavors

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	BETA	T	SIG. (P)	TOLERANCE	VIF
Neophobia	0.150	3.147	.002**	0.998	1.002
Neophilia	0.427	8.936	.000**	0.998	1.002
F		43.845			
R		0.447			
Adjusted R²		0.195			
Durbin-Watson		1.944			

*The value is significant at the 0.05 level **The value is significant at the 0.01 level

Source: own elaboration.

The model explained 19.5% (R²) of the attitude changes toward street tastes. The relevant table showed that the effect of neophobia and neophilia on the attitude toward street tastes was linear and positive. Both neophobic and neophilic tendencies positively affected the students' attitudes toward street tastes. When compared, the neophilic tendency was more potent than the neophobic tendency.

In addition, if there is more than one variable, the Tolerance and VIF values should be examined to understand

whether there is a multicollinearity problem between the variables (Keskin, Solunoğlu, and Aktaş, 2020). The tolerance value should be >0.10, and the VIF value should be <5 (Hair, 2005).

No multicollinearity problem appeared in the relevant table. The value expressing autocorrelation between the independent variables is the Durbin-Watson value and should be between 1.5 and 2.5 (Kalaycı, 2006). Also, the relevant value exhibited no autocorrelation problem.

While the positive effect of neophilia on the general attitude towards street tastes was an anticipatable approach, the positive impact of neophobia on the attitude towards street flavors was surprising and remarkable. The current study results were similar to those of the Ha Heonsu (2016)

and Lee et al. (2019) studies in terms of the positive neophilia effect on attitude toward street tastes but different from them in the positive neophobia effect. In this case, the H1 and H2 hypotheses were accepted.

Table5. Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Neophobic and Neophilic Tendencies on the Attitude Toward Food Quality.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	BETA	T	SIG. (P)	TOLERANCE	VIF
Neophobia	0.141	2.914	.004**	0.998	1.002
Neophilia	0.406	8.382	.000**	0.998	1.002
F		38.478			
R		0.424			
Adjusted R²		0.175			
Durbin-Watson		1.887			

* The value is significant at the 0.05 level ** The value is significant at the 0.01 level.

Source: own elaboration.

The model explained 17.5% (R²) of the attitude changes toward street delicacies. The data showed that the food neophobia and neophilia of the students affected the attitude toward food quality linearly and positively. Again, the neophilic tendency in participants was more effective than the neophobic tendency. In general, the neophobic and

neophilic tendencies of the students positively affected their attitude toward food quality in street flavors.

Table 6 shows the results of multiple regression analysis on the effect of students' neophobia and neophilia tendencies on their attitudes toward service quality.

Table 6. Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Neophobia and Neophilia Tendencies on the Attitude Toward Service Quality.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	BETA	T	SIG. (P)	TOLERANCE	VIF
Neophobia	0.155	3.205	.001**	0.998	1.002
Neophilia	0.407	8.444	.000**	0.998	1.002
F		39.786			
R		0.430			
Adjusted R²		0.180			
Durbin-Watson		2.002			

* The value is significant at the 0.05 level ** The value is significant at the 0.01 level

Source: own elaboration.

The model explained 18% (R²) of the attitude change towards street tastes. The effect of food neophobia and neophilia tendency on the attitude toward service quality was linear and positive.

of Tracy (2020). It can be suggested that delicious, quick-prepared street tastes with unusual presentations of the street vendors displaying friendly and fun attitudes may affect this result.

In general, students' neophobic and neophilic tendencies positively affected their attitudes toward service quality in street flavors. This result complied with the results

Table 7 shows the results of multiple regression analysis on the effect of students' neophobia and neophilia tendencies on their attitude towards pleasure.

Table 7. Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Neophobia and Neophilia Tendencies on the Attitude Towards Pleasure.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	BETA	T	SIG. (P)	TOLERANCE	VIF
Neophobia	0.087	1.834	.068	0.998	1.002
Neophilia	0.456	9.624	.000**	0.998	1.002
F		47.370			
R		0.461			
Adjusted R²		0.208			
Durbin-Watson		1.961			

* The value is significant at the 0.05 level ** The value is significant at the 0.01 level.

Source: own elaboration.

The model explained 20.8% (R²) of the attitude change toward street delicacies. The effect of food neophilia tendency on the attitude toward pleasure was linear and positive, but neophobia displayed no significant impact (sig.0.680>0.05). The neophilic tendency characterized by a positive approach to novelty is both a social and an individual trait. Neophiliacs associate trying new foods with positive feelings like excitement, variety, and complexity. They

describe encountering unknown foods as an "adventurous" part of social life (Veeck 2010). In this context, it is possible that street tastes—usually presented in a fun atmosphere, making a social difference for individuals—may have influenced this finding.

Table 8 shows the results of multiple regression analysis on the effect of students' neophobia and neophilia tendencies on their attitudes towards hygiene quality.

Table 8. Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Neophobia and Neophilia Tendencies on the Attitude towards Hygiene.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	BETA	T	SIG. (P)	TOLERANCE	VIF
Neophobia	0.104	1.881	.048*	0.998	1.002
Neophilia	0.159	3.020	.003**	0.998	1.002
F		6.299			
R		0.186			
Adjusted R²		0.029			
Durbin-Watson		2.013			

* The value is significant at the 0.05 level ** The value is significant at the 0.01 level.

Source: own elaboration.

The model explained 29% (R^2) attitude change towards street delicacies. The effects of both food neophobia and neophilia tendencies on the attitudes toward hygiene were linear and positive. Students' neophobic and neophilic tendencies positively impacted their attitudes toward hygiene in street tastes. Remarkably, the more neophobia increased, the more the attitude toward hygiene positively increased.

Despite students' negative attitudes towards hygiene, their steady consumption of street delicacies supported this result.

Table 9 shows the results of multiple regression analysis on the effect of students' neophobia and neophilia tendencies on their attitudes towards the price sub-dimension.

Table 9. Multiple Regression Analysis on the Effect of Neophobia and Neophilia Tendencies on the Attitude Towards Price.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	BETA	T	SIG. (P)	TOLERANCE	VIF
Neophobia	0.064	1.239	.216	0.998	1.002
Neophilia	0.275	5.355	.000**	0.998	1.002
F		14.869			
R		0.279			
Adjusted R²		0.073			
Durbin-Watson		1.944			

*The value is significant at the 0.05 level **The value is significant at the 0.01 level.

Source: own elaboration.

The model explains 73% (R^2) of the attitude change towards street delicacies. The effect of food neophilia tendency on attitude towards price sub-dimension was linear and positive, whereas the impact of neophobia tendency was insignificant (sig. 0.216 > 0.005). The higher desire of neophilics to consume new flavors and the satisfaction with

street foods in terms of variety, taste, and product quality may have affected this result.

Table 10 shows the results of multiple regression analysis on the effect of students' neophobia and neophilia tendencies on their attitudes toward the satisfaction sub-dimension.

Table 10. Multiple Regression Analysis of the Effect of Neophobia and Neophilia Tendencies on the Attitude Towards Satisfaction Subdimension.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	BETA	T	SIG. (P)	TOLERANCE	VIF
Neophobia	0.113	2.197	.029*	0.998	1.002
Neophilia	0.246	4.768	.000**	0.998	1.002
F		13.390			
R		0.266			
Adjusted R²		0.066			
Durbin-Watson		2.042			

* The value is significant at the 0.05 level ** The value is significant at the 0.01 level.

Source: own elaboration.

The model explained 66% (R^2) attitude change toward street tastes. The effects of both food neophobia and neophilia tendencies of students on the satisfaction sub-dimension were linear and positive.

In general, students' neophobia and neophilia tendencies positively affected their attitudes toward satisfaction with street tastes. This result might be associated with high food and service quality in Türkiye.

After examining the analysis results in general terms, the **H3** hypothesis was partially accepted, while the **H4** was totally accepted.

4.1.3 Consumption Frequency of Street Tastes

This research investigated the frequency of students' weekly street foods consumption. Table 11 shows the students' street foods consumption frequencies.

Table 11. Street foods Consumption Frequency.

	Frequency	Percentage
I Never Consume	11	3.1
Once a week	219	61.9
Two-Three Times a Week	103	29.1
Four-Five Times a Week	17	4.8
Every day	4	1.1
Total	354	%100

Source: own elaboration.

As seen in Table 11, of the students, 61% consumed street food once a week, 29% two to three times a week, 4.8% four to five times a week, and 1.1% every day. 3.1% of the students consumed no street delicacies at all. This weekly study results were similar to the results of the studies conducted on students by Sert and Kapusuz (2010) and Şanlıer et al. (2018).

In general, although the students had negative attitudes towards the hygiene sub-dimension of street tastes, most of them steadily consumed street delicacies. While this result supported the study results conducted by Sert and Kapusuz (2010), Şanlıer et al. (2018), and Sünnetçiöğlü and Yıldırım (2019), it differed from the results of the study conducted by Ha Heonsu (2016). On the other hand, the most consumed street foods were doner kebab, Turkish bagel, and ice cream.

5 DIFFERENCE ANALYSIS RESULTS BETWEEN THE PARTICIPANTS' NEOPHOBIC AND NEOPHILIC TENDENCIES AND ATTITUDES TOWARD STREET FLAVORS, ACCORDING TO THEIR DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

In this part, this research, using the parametric tests One Way Anova and t-test, determined whether there was a significant difference between students' neophobia and neophilia tendencies and attitudes towards street flavors according to their demographic characteristics.

One Way Anova was conducted to reveal the difference between participants' hometowns and their attitudes towards street flavors (food quality, service quality, pleasure, hygiene, price, satisfaction). Table 12 shows the analysis results.

Table 12. Difference Analysis on Attitudes Towards Street Flavors and Participants' hometowns (One Way Anova).

Attitudes Toward Sub-Dimensions in Street Tastes	Hometown	N	Mean	SD	F	Sig. (p)	Difference (Tukey)
Attitudes Toward Food Quality (AFQ)	City ^a	175	3.72	0.080	3.211	.042*	b-c
	District ^b	120	3.82	0.56			
	Village/Town ^c	59	3.52	0.89			
Attitudes Toward Service Quality (ASQ)	City ^a	175	3.95	0.72	4.824	.009*	c-a c-b
	District ^b	120	4.00	0.64			
	Village/Town ^c	59	3.65	0.91			
Attitudes Toward Pleasure (APL)	City ^a	175	4.15	0.86	3.830	.023*	c-a c-b
	District ^b	120	4.13	0.88			
	Village/Town ^c	59	3.78	1.12			
Attitudes Toward Hygiene (AHGN)	City ^a	175	2.59	0.90	0.388	.679	-
	District ^b	120	2.60	0.82			
	Village/Town ^c	59	2.70	0.94			
Attitudes Toward Price (APRC)	City ^a	175	4.02	0.93	0.698	.498	-
	District ^b	120	4.01	0.89			
	Village/Town ^c	59	3.86	1.08			
Attitudes Toward Satisfaction (ASTF)	City ^a	175	3.57	0.95	0.767	.465	-
	District ^b	120	3.48	0.86			
	Village/Town ^c	59	3.41	1.07			
The General Attitude Toward Street Tastes	City ^a	175	3.67	0.67	2.487	.085	-
	District ^b	120	3.70	0.56			
	Village/Town ^c	59	3.48	0.77			

*p<0.05

Levels of Participation: 1: Strongly Disagree,..5: Strongly Agree.

Source: own elaboration.

The analysis revealed a statistically significant difference between the participants' attitudes toward food quality according to their places of origin (p<0.05). The mean AFQ level of the students from a village or town (avg=3.52) was lower than those coming from a district (avg=3.82). The mean AFQ level of the students from a city was higher than those from a village or town.

Furthermore, there was a statistically significant difference between the APL level of the participants according to their places of origin (p<0.05). The mean APL level of participants from a village or town (avg=3.78) was lower than those from a city (avg=4.15) or district (avg=4.13). Hence, the attitude toward pleasure in the street tastes was less in students from a village or town than in those living in a city or district.

The H6 hypothesis was partially accepted after analyzing the differences in attitudes toward street tastes according to the demographic characteristics of the students. Solunoğlu (2018) also revealed that the participants' attitudes toward street tastes differed according to their demographic traits. The current study was partially similar to the Solunoğlu study (2018) in this respect.

The T-test was conducted to reveal the difference between the participants' attitudes towards neophobia, neophilia, and street tastes (food quality, service quality, pleasure, hygiene, price, and satisfaction) according to their departments. Table 13 shows the analysis results.

Table 13. Difference Analysis of Students by Department (t-Test).

Variables	Department	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig. (p)
Neophobia	Cookery	193	2.84	0.89	1.651	.100
	Gastronomy	161	2.69	0.81		
Neophilia	Cookery	193	3.74	0.99	-3.113	.002*
	Gastronomy	161	4.02	0.72		
Food quality	Cookery	193	3.64	0.80	-2.144	.033*
	Gastronomy	161	3.81	0.67		
Service Quality	Cookery	193	3.86	0.79	-0.596	.111
	Gastronomy	161	3.99	0.66		
Pleasure	Cookery	193	3.96	1.03	-2.770	.006*
	Gastronomy	161	4.23	0.76		
Hygiene	Cookery	193	2.66	0.93	1.101	.271
	Gastronomy	161	2.56	0.81		
Price	Cookery	193	3.95	1.04	-0.895	.371
	Gastronomy	161	4.04	0.82		
Satisfaction	Cookery	193	3.49	1.00	-0.517	.605
	Gastronomy	161	3.54	0.87		
General Attitude Toward Street Tastes	Cookery	193	3.60	0.72	-1.547	.114
	Gastronomy	161	3.71	0.56		

*p<0.05

Levels of Participation: 1: Strongly Disagree, ..., 5: Strongly Agree.

Source: own elaboration.

T-test by the department revealed a statistically significant difference in the attitudes toward neophilia, food quality, and pleasure variables ($p < 0.05$). The cookery department students' neophilic tendencies ($avg = 3.74$) and their attitudes toward food quality ($avg = 3.64$) and pleasure ($avg = 3.96$) were lower than the gastronomy department students.

In other words, the neophilia tendency of gastronomy students was higher than that of cookery students. In addition, gastronomy students' attitudes toward food quality

and pleasure in street flavors were higher than cookery students. Thus, the **H5** hypothesis was accepted.

On the other hand, this research examined participants' other demographic data in the survey, nevertheless, as most students were in the same age group, and their marital status was single, these demographic data were not evaluated. The difference analysis showed that the neophobia or neophilia tendencies of the students and their attitudes towards street tastes did not differ according to gender, class, and internship status.

Table 14. Hypothesis results.

Hypothesis	Decision
H1: Students' neophobic tendencies affect their general attitudes toward street tastes.	Supported
H2: Students' neophilic tendencies affect their general attitudes toward street tastes.	Supported
H3: Students' neophobic tendencies affect the sub-dimensions of street tastes.	Partially Supported
H4: Students' neophilic tendencies affect the sub-dimensions of street tastes.	Supported
H5: Neophobia and neophilia tendencies of students differ according to their demographic characteristics.	Supported
H6: Students' general attitudes towards street flavors differ according to demographic characteristics.	Partially Supported

Source: own elaboration.

The hypotheses developed within the scope of the research were tested and the results of all hypotheses are summarized in Table 14. In this context, it is possible to say that hypotheses H1, H2, H4 and H5 are supported, while hypotheses H3 and H5 are partially supported.

6 CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION, AND SUGGESTIONS

6.1 Theoretical Implications

The current study, also investigating the students' general neophobia and neophilia averages, found that the neophilia tendencies were higher than the neophobia tendencies. In other words, students generally had a neophilic disposition. In the study, the general average score of the attitudes toward street tastes was 3.65, indicating that the students generally had positive attitudes toward street tastes.

The averages of the attitudes toward pleasure, price, service quality, food quality, satisfaction, and hygiene sub-dimensions of street tastes were 4.08, 3.99, 3.92, 3.72, 3.51, and 2.61, respectively. While the pleasure dimension had the highest average, the hygiene dimension had remarkably the lowest.

This result revealed that students were concerned about hygiene and food safety in street foods. However, despite this result, the students were apparently not so much willing to give up the street delicacies. In this direction, the sense of pleasure, food quality, and service quality experienced in street delicacies overshadowed the hygiene factor.

On the other hand, the study sought to reveal the effect of neophobic and neophilic tendencies on the attitude toward street tastes. The regression analysis showed that neophobia (0.150) and neophilia (0.427) tendencies had a

linear and positive effect on the general attitude towards street tastes. In this context, the authors concluded that the students' neophobic and neophilic tendencies positively affected their attitudes toward street tastes.

The current study supported the results of similar research in the relevant literature (Ha Heonsu, 2016; Lee et al., 2019; Tracy, 2020). It was an unexpected and remarkable result that neophobia positively affected the attitude toward street tastes. The comparison of the two tendencies disclosed that neophilia had a more powerful impact than neophobia.

The students' neophobia had a linear positive effect on their attitudes toward food quality, service quality, hygiene, and satisfaction sub-dimensions of street tastes. On the other hand, neophilia had a linear positive effect on their attitudes toward food quality, service quality, pleasure, hygiene, price, and satisfaction. In other words, neophilia positively affected the attitude toward all sub-dimensions of street tastes.

Neophilic individuals had more positive attitudes toward street flavors than neophobic individuals. The study, which contributed to the literature on the effect of neophobic and neophilic tendencies on the attitude toward street tastes, had similar results to previous studies.

This research also examined whether students' neophobic/neophilic tendencies and attitudes toward street tastes differed according to the demographic characteristics and found some differences according to their places of origin and departments. The study determined that the attitude toward food quality, service quality, and pleasure in street tastes differed according to hometowns.

This result might relate to the fact that those residing in urban areas are more exposed to street flavors than those living in rural areas. Furthermore, neophilic tendency, food quality, and pleasure in street flavors differed according to departments. The neophilic tendency of the gastronomy students (mean=4.02) was higher than cookery students (mean=3.74).

The possible reason for this situation could be that gastronomy students were more exposed to new/unfamiliar foods because of more intensive and long-term education. In addition, the attitudes of gastronomy students towards food quality (avg=3.81) and pleasure (avg=4.23) in street flavors were higher than those of cookery students (avg=3.64 and avg=3.96, respectively).

6.2 Practical Implications

The research results underline that the tendency of food neophobia and neophilia is a crucial point for chef candidates. Students' higher neophilia tendencies compared to neophobia might be an advantage in their professional development. Food and beverage businesses aiming to gain a competitive advantage and implement original ideas should employ qualified and innovative personnel (Tekeli and Özkoç, 2022). Therefore, cooks and chefs in the ever-changing and developing food and beverage industry should be open-minded to original and unusual products, distinct culinary cultures, and cooking techniques.

Since neophilic chefs are more willing to try new foods, they might be more creative than neophobic chefs and more successful in gastronomy trends that reflect world cuisines,

such as fusion cuisine. On the other hand, neophobic chefs might have no opportunity to create exciting and surprising menus and recipes because they are closed to new and (or) exotic foods. Hence, students must develop neophilic attitudes during their gastronomy and culinary education for their professional careers. For this, the present study made some suggestions below:

The students must taste different culinary cultures as frequently as possible in exotic restaurants to increase their neophilic tendencies and develop their palate. Interning in the sector without wasting time during the education or summer holidays will help them try and compare new foods. So, students' neophobia will decrease, while their neophilic tendency will develop. Students' experiences abroad will increase their interaction with different culinary cultures and reduce their neophobia tendencies. Students should participate in exchange programs or international internship opportunities, which will positively affect their professional development.

Students' participation in alternative authentic culinary classes, foreign chefs' visits to universities as guest lecturers, universities' more intensive practical training, and informative and educational seminar organizations about new products and trends will reduce their food neophobia and increase neophilic tendencies. On the other hand, prospective chefs' personality traits also affect their attitudes toward food. In particular, neophilic individuals have a more positive attitude toward foods. The research findings determined that students had positive attitudes toward street flavors. Food quality, service quality, price, satisfaction, and pleasure variables significantly attract students to prefer street tastes.

However, hygiene in street delicacies is a matter of concern for students. Students have a negative attitude toward the hygiene of street foods, which suggests that street vendors do not pay close attention to hygiene. Besides, the related literature calls attention to another point: *some street vendors have sufficient knowledge about hygiene but ignore it in practice*. The food safety problem may arise from environmental conditions, the sellers, or public institutions. In light of these results, some suggestions of the research authors are as follows:

Street vendors should have better service area conditions. For example, stationary street vendors should have clean water sources, containers where they can leave waste regularly, and closed areas for food storage. Public institutions should provide necessary training on hygiene, sanitation, food safety, food preservation techniques, and food cooking techniques to street vendors and inspect them.

As generally known, many street vendors work illegally and out of the inspection. Standardization and legal obligations, such as licenses, might increase food quality, reduce food safety risks, and allow "controlled growth" in the sector. Street delicacies are one of the prominent attraction elements, especially for gastronomic tourism. Therefore, authorities should offer opportunities to improve and encourage street vendors through marketing and promotional activities instead of driving them away from the sector. In this regard, special areas should be created with the proper infrastructure and superstructure for street vendors, and their authentic street delicacies should be attraction centers for tourists.

6.3 Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

This study aimed to evaluate the attitudes towards street tastes specific to the Phrygian region. However, the lack of previous research on region-specific street flavors has created a limitation. It is necessary to carry out mapping studies for regional authentic street delicacies in Türkiye. In addition, the study was limited to gastronomy and cookery students studying in the Phrygian region. It may be recommended to conduct studies aimed at different regions and populations.

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CRedit author statement

Term	Definition	1 st Author	2 nd Author
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	x	x
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	x	x
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	x	x
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	x	x
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	x	x
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	x	x
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	x	x
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	x	x
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	x	x
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or postpublication stages	x	x
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	x	x
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	x	x
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution		x
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	x	x

Source: reproduced from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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